

Fostering a Culture of Inclusive and Fair Open Science Infrastructure in the Asia Pacific

Akashi, Eliko

akashieliko@keio.jp
Keio University Global Research Institute, Keio University, Japan

Miyakita, Goki

5ki-miyakita@kmd.keio.ac.jp
Keio Museum Commons, Keio University, Japan; Research Institute for Digital Media and Content, Keio University, Japan

Okawa, Keiko

keiko@kmd.keio.ac.jp
Graduate School of Media Design, Keio University, Japan

Introduction

As the digital transformation proceeds, the pandemic increased Internet penetration, from 3.4 billion people in 2017 to 4.9 billion in 2022, which brought 63 percent of the world population to become Internet users (ITU 2022). The Internet has become vital in our daily lives, and the volume and way of people's communication have transformed significantly (Haider / Sundin 2019, Redshaw 2020, Rideout et al. 2022). Especially in the humanities domain, the Internet enables researchers to collaborate globally, mobilizes more stakeholders, and strengthens the connection between research and society (Führ / Bisset Alvarez 2021, McGillivray 2020, Milligan 2013).

Foundation

On top of Internet use, there is a growing movement of Open Science (OS). In November 2021, the first universal framework on OS—the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (UNESCO 2021) was adopted by 193 countries. This “global standard-setting instrument” (Azoulay 2021) is considered to be a milestone for our research as well as society, however, the practices of OS “often overlooking important initiatives in the arts, humanities and social sciences” (Tennant et al. 2020: 13) where substantial challenges remain (Camkin et al. 2022, Knöchelmann 2019, Longley Arthur / Hearn 2021). Indeed, the OS movement encompasses various subjects and approaches (Ayris / Ignat 2018, Ramachandran et al. 2021), and while there are relevant studies within the intersection of humanities and OS (e.g., Chan 2019, de Jong et al. 2020, El Khatib et al. 2020, ESF 2011, Okune et al. 2018), this paper stands unique in building an Open Science Infrastructure (OSI) that can support not only necessary infrastructural services but also a community and knowledge-based framework.

Project Overview

Since 2001, School on Internet Asia (SOI-Asia) Project¹, a platform for inter-university educational programs among 29 higher education research institutions from 13 countries, has been fostering collaboration activities with the support of Research and Education Networks (RENs) (Okawa 2010) [Figure 1]. Although this project initially started by offering STEM-based activities, starting in 2021, the following sub-projects have been launched alongside the three pillars: a) Advanced Technology, b) Knowledge Base, and c) Community Building [Figure 2] to stimulate collaboration across borders and lead interdisciplinary initiatives in the fair and inclusive implementation of OSI in the humanities.

Figure 1 Geographic Map of the SOI-Asia Project Partner Institutions (Red Squares)

a) Advanced Technology: Satellite and Aero Research and Educational Network (SARENA-PAC) and Arterial Research and Educational Network (ARENA-PAC) Projects²

Despite the growth of Internet users, the inefficiencies in Internet connectivity remain a challenge in certain Asian countries (Dae Keun / Chang Yong 2022). This project focuses on creating an Internet infrastructure to foster stable international research and education network in the Asia Pacific. SARENA-PAC and ARENA-PAC are the backbone networks and are made up of an international submarine cable network constructed with the goal of expanding the Internet in the Asia Pacific.

b) Knowledge Base: Asia Pacific Internet Engineering (APIE) Program³

APIE Program aims to foster and support people to learn the necessary Internet engineering skills and how to improve cyberspace for society to manage the internet infrastructure. The program collaborates with lecturers from SOI Asia member institutions and is open to undergrad/grad students, despite their major being in another field [Figure 2].

Figure 2 Photos from the APIE Program

c) Community Building: Evidence Based Approach (EBA) Project⁴

The EBA project aims to foster an Asia Pacific-wide collaborative community among universities to design an evidence-based resilient future society. The project offers a curriculum to foster human resources capable of identifying and tackling issues based on evidence and analysis. Currently, EBA offers a fieldwork program for under-grad/grad students where they learn and apply skills to address common issues in real-life situations and further promote cross-disciplinary scholarship while building a community of practice [Figure 3].

Figure 3 Photos from the EBA Project

Summary

The aim of this presentation is to explore the practices and experiences we have learned from developing the OSI, and further shares our ongoing action plan for fostering a culture of inclusive and fair OS in the Asia Pacific. The described three-pillar model functions as a collaboration-led infrastructure landscape across disciplines and countries. In tackling the following questions, we believe this study will make a meaningful contribution to the realm of (digital) humanities and beyond.

- How we can broaden and deepen the adoption of open science methods amongst humanities scholars.
- How we can represent and increase the profile of humanities within the open science endeavor.
- How we can develop research environments and platforms around humanities practitioners.

Notes

1. SOI-Asia Project Website: <https://www.soi.asia/>
2. ARENA-PAC Project Website: <https://www.arena-pac.net/>
3. APIE Program Website: <https://apie.soi.asia/>
4. EBA Project Website: <https://eba.soi.asia/>

Bibliography

- Ayris, Paul / Ignat, Tiberius** . (2018): “Defining the role of libraries in the Open Science landscape: a reflection on current European practice”, in: *Open Information Science* , 2 (1), 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.1515/opis-2018-0001> .
- Azoulay, Audrey** (2021): “UNESCO embraces open science to shape society’s future”, in: *Nature* , 593, 341. doi:10.1038/d41586-021-01338-8.
- Camkin, J. / Neto, S. / Bhattarai, B. / Ojha, H. / Khan, S. / Sugiura, A. / Lin, J. / Nurritasari, F. A. / Karanja, J. M.** (2022): “Open Science for Accelerating the Sustainable Development

Goals: Status and Prospects in Asia and the Pacific”, in: *Frontiers in Political Science* , Vol. 4, DOI=10.3389/fpos.2022.878761.

Chan, Leslie / Okune, Angela / Hillyer, Rebecca / Albornoz, Denisse / Posada, Alejandro (Eds.) (2019): *Contextualizing Openness: Situating Open Science* . Ottawa: University of Ottawa Press. <https://www.idrc.ca/en/book/contextualizing-openness-situating-open-science> [25.04.2023].

Dae Keun, C. / Chang Yong, S. (2022): “Promoting ICT connectivity through internet exchange points in South-East Asia”, in: *Asia-Pacific Information Superhighway (AP-IS) Working Paper Series* , United Nations ESCAP, ICT and Disaster Risk Reduction Division.

de Jong, F.M.G. / Maegaard, Bente / Fišer, Darja / Van Uytvanck, Dieter / Witt, Andreas (2020): “Interoperability in an Infrastructure Enabling Multidisciplinary Research: The case of CLARIN”, in: *Proceedings of the 12th Language Resources and Evaluation Conference* , 3406. European Language Resources Association (ELRA) <https://www.aclweb.org/anthology/2020.l-rec-1.417/> [25.04.2023].

El Khatib, Randa / Arbuckle, Alyssa / Siemens, Lynne / Siemens, Ray / Winter, Caroline / ETCL Research Group (2020): “An “Open Lab?” The Electronic Textual Cultures Lab in the Evolving Digital Humanities Landscape”, in: *Digital Humanities Quarterly* 14 (3): n.p. <http://www.digitalhumanities.org/dhq/vol/14/3/000480/000480.html> [25.04.2023].

ESF - European Science Foundation (2011): *Research Infrastructures in the Digital Humanities. Science Policy Briefing 42* . Strasbourg: ESF. http://www.esf.org/fileadmin/Public_documents/Publications/spb42_RI_DigitalHumanities.pdf http://www.esf.org/fileadmin/Public_documents/Publications/spb42_RI_DigitalHumanities.pdf [25.04.2023].

Führ, F. / Bisset Alvarez, E. (2021): “Digital humanities and open science: initial aspects”, in: Bisset Álvarez, E. (ed.): *DIONE 2021* . Lecture Notes of the Institute for Computer Sciences, Social Informatics and Telecommunications Engineering, vol 378, pp. 154–173. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-77417-2_12.

Haider, J. / Sundin, O. (2019): *Invisible Search and Online Search Engines: The Ubiquity of Search in Everyday Life* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429448546>.

International Telecommunication Union (ITU) (2022): *Global Connectivity Report 2022* . <https://www.itu.int/hub/publication/d-ind-global-01-2022/> [25.04.2023].

Knöchelmann, Marcel (2019): “Open science in the humanities, or: Open humanities?”, in: *Publications* , 7(4), 65. <https://doi.org/10.3390/publications7040065>.

Longley Arthur, P. / Hearn, L. (2021): “Toward open research: A narrative review of the challenges and opportunities for open humanities”, in: *Journal of Communication* , 71(5), 827–853, <https://doi.org/10.1093/joc/jqab028>.

Tennant, Jonathan / Agarwal, Ritwik / Baždarić, Ksenija / Brassard, David / Crick, Tom / Dunleavy, Daniel J. / Evans, Thomas R., et al. (2020): A Tale of Two ‘opens’: Intersections Between Free and Open Source Software and Open Scholarship. SocArXiv. doi:10.31235/osf.io/2kxq8.

McGillivray, B. / Alex, B. / Ames, S. / Armstrong, G. / Beavan, D. / Ciula, A. / Colavizza, G., et al. (2020): *The challenges and prospects of the intersection of humanities and data science: A white paper from The Alan Turing Institute*. Alan Turing Institute. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.12732164>.

Milligan, Ian (2012): “Mining the ‘Internet Graveyard’: Re-thinking the Historians’ Toolkit”, in: *Journal of the Canadian His-*

torical Association/Revue de la Société historique du Canada , 23(2), pp.21-64. <https://doi.org/10.7202/1015788ar>.

Okawa, Keiko (2010): “Global education for global issues: lessons learned from SOI ASIA project”, Conference presentation at *International symposium on Global Campus for Sustainability Education* (October 29, 2010), Hokkaido University, Japan. https://eprints.lib.hokudai.ac.jp/dspace/bitstream/2115/44147/1/32_1Okawa.pdf [25.04.2023].

Okune, Angela / Hillyer, Rebecca / Albornoz, Denisse / Posada, Alejandro / Chan, Leslie (2018): “Whose Infrastructure? Towards Inclusive and Collaborative Knowledge Infrastructures in Open Science”, in: *ELPUB 2018* , Jun 2018, Toronto, Canada. <https://doi.org/10.4000/proceedings.elpub.2018.31>.

Ramachandran, R. / Bugbee, K. / Murphy, K. (2021): “From open data to open science”, in: *Earth and Space Science* , 8, e2020EA001562. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020EA001562>.

Redshaw, Tom (2020): “What Is Digital Society? Reflections on the Aims and Purpose of Digital Sociology”, in: *Sociology* , 54(2), 425–431. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0038038519880114>.

Rideout, V. / Peebles, A. / Mann, S. / Robb, M. B. (2022): *Common Sense. Census: Media Use by Tweens and Teens, 2021* , Common Sense, San Francisco, CA.

UNESCO - United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (2021): *UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science* . <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000379949.locale=en> [25.04.2023].